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YANTO A.

Department of Library and Information Science, Universitas Padjadjaran (Bandung, Indonesia),
e-mail: andri.yanto@unpad.ac.id, ORCID 0000-0001-7041-0134

PRIJANA P.

Department of Library and Information Science, Universitas Padjadjaran (Bandung, Indonesia),
e-mail: prijana@unpad.ac.id, ORCID 0000-0003-3290-0938

NURSARI T.

Universitas Padjadjaran (Bandung, Indonesia), e-mail: tita19002@mail.unpad.ac.id,
ORCID 0009-0001-5315-3460

The Contribution of Special Libraries in Promoting Social Inclusion in Indonesia

Objective. The majority of special libraries fulfill the information needs of their work environment to support the development and improvement of the duties and functions of the institution and its human resources. However, several service innovations have been carried out by creating social inclusion-based service programs for the general public. One is the Center for Library and Dissemination of Agricultural Technology (PUSTAKA) of the Ministry of Agriculture, Indonesia. This research aims to provide an overview of how the PUSTAKA special library can be involved in creating service innovations for the public through social inclusion programs. **Methods.** The method used is a qualitative method with a library research approach. **Results.** The study results illustrate that PUSTAKA has extended its reach to communities with limited agricultural collections and information access. The library has also become a maker space for entrepreneurship awareness and creativity, enhancing the potential of the community related to agriculture. PUSTAKA serves as a knowledge hub for agriculture, boasting vast agricultural resources. Furthermore, the library uses information technology to provide virtual services, expanding its reach and promoting agricultural literacy in remote areas. PUSTAKA's multifaceted approach to serving the community highlights its commitment to agricultural education and inclusive social services. **Conclusions.** The research concludes that PUSTAKA as a special library has implemented social inclusion in contributing to the community by improving the skills of farmers, promoting agricultural literacy, and extending access to agricultural collections and information.

Keywords: social inclusion; library transformation; special library; information services

Introduction

The library contributes to providing access to the resources it owns and collaborates with various community components in the literacy movement. The library's presence is expected to enhance the knowledge and skills of the community. This aligns with the primary goal of a library, which is to make the community lifelong learners (Lusiana, Yanto, & CMS, 2023). The existence of libraries in Indonesia is closely related to the overseeing institution of the library. One example is the libraries that operate under government ministries or agencies to serve the readers associated with their overseeing institutions.

The majority of special libraries fulfill the information needs of their work environment to support the development and improvement of the duties and functions of the institution and its human resources. However, several service innovations have been carried out by creating social inclusion-based service programs for the general public. One such special library is the Center for Library and Dissemination of Agricultural Technology (PUSTAKA) of the Ministry of Agriculture, Indonesia. The Center for Library and Dissemination of Agricultural Technology (PUSTAKA) of the Ministry of Agriculture is one of the special libraries that provides information for the public, particularly for the farming community. The literacy movement has become a

national collective effort that involves multiple stakeholders to create a literate society, as stated by Suharso et al. (Suharso, Yanto, Rohman, Wiratningsih, & Saefullah, 2018).

PUSTAKA has also established Reading Gardens as a socially inclusive library facility by implementing programs that actively involve the community in response to and in support of socially inclusive library policies to enhance the quality and well-being of society. Special government institution libraries also have a responsibility to provide information access across various scopes (Sembiring & Wijayanti, 2020).

Lusiana et al. (2022) mention that TBM (Reading Gardens) serves as a complete and up-to-date information hub for developing knowledge, skills, and behaviors/attitudes. TBMs have evolved into learning centers, and some have taken on the role of empowerment centers for the community (Lusiana, Yanto, Anwar, & Komala, 2019). TBMs are institutions that facilitate personal and community development, especially in promoting a reading culture among the public (Yanto, Rodiah, & Lusiana, 2016). TBM provides reading materials as a source of community learning. The existence of this reading is expected to support lifelong community learning and can add insight in applying various practical skills directly, such as farming (Dwiyantoro, 2019).

Social inclusion-based literacy programs conducted by the special library PUSTAKA can play a role and serve as a model for other government institution libraries (Sembiring & Wijayanti, 2020). PUSTAKA has developed programs aligned with the Ministry of Agriculture's mission to achieve advanced, self-sufficient, and modern agriculture with the goal of sustainable prosperity and sovereignty for farmers (Sutarsyah, Rufaidah, & Suryantini, 2021). These programs are in line with PUSTAKA's core responsibilities of managing libraries and disseminating information on agricultural knowledge and technology. The information collected indicates that PUSTAKA has made efforts to provide agricultural information in digital form available over the internet for readers, farmers, and the general public in need of agricultural information. This research aims to provide an overview of how the PUSTAKA special library can be involved in creating service innovations for the public through social inclusion programs.

Methods

The method used in this study is library research. According to Zed (2008), library research is a method that involves collecting data by understanding and studying theories from various literature related to the research. There are four stages of library research in this study, including preparing the necessary tools for literature search, preparing a working bibliography, organizing time, and reading or taking notes on research materials. The research materials include journals related to social inclusion services in special libraries and various reports related to socially inclusive activities in special libraries. All the obtained library materials are analyzed thoroughly to strengthen the propositions developed in this study.

Results and Discussion

The development of internet-based communication technology and digital technology has enabled the public to access a vast amount of information quickly. Almost all types of information are available in various forms, including text, images, and videos. However, many community members still need help selecting and accessing information that suits their specific needs. One such group is farmers and those interested in agriculture who need help accessing specialized information. In this case, the role of special libraries is so important in providing and disseminating information for communities with specific needs. Now, the role of special libraries is not only felt

by certain communities, but society in general. The social inclusion concept helps special libraries contribute more to society.

Special libraries have helped people increase their abilities and awareness regarding social issues that are rarely paid attention to. They have special programs to attract people to get involved in various programs that can provide more insight and skills to the community. Social inclusion has become a concern in several parts of the country, which has become a concern in improving social justice for society. In social inclusion activities, the use of technology is very useful for improving services and increasing access so that the programs implemented can have more impact.

Technology-based literacy activities are also carried out by PUSTAKA. Information literacy activities are carried out to support the Ministry of Agriculture's program in realizing advanced, independent and modern agriculture. All information literacy activities that have been carried out virtually can be watched on the Youtube channel PUSTAKA Ministry of Agriculture's. Like the activities carried out by the special library in China, namely, the Human Library, through a web-based project, StoryAd (jchumanlibrarieshub.asia or human.asia), involves the public to create stories about social issues such as disabilities, gender identity issues, and mental illness, which are then published on the website. In the next stage, story readers can invite the main characters of the story to meet face-to-face through a workshop.

Chan (2019) found that the StoryAd model turns audiences into partners and collaborators through the stories they collect. Through the workshops, participants demonstrated increased open-mindedness and positive attitudes toward themselves and were open to other people's points of view. In America, medical libraries achieve social inclusion through social justice by implementing various programs providing health information to the HIV/AIDS community and communities suffering from mental illness (Martin, 2019). Libraries network with community-based organizations to further advance social justice by increasing information literacy in underserved populations. The library also developed special mechanisms to access HIV/AIDS community-based information.

In Indonesia, PUSTAKA, a specialized library focused on agricultural information and the dissemination of agricultural technology, has extended its reach to communities with limited access to agricultural collections and information. This outreach is achieved by establishing a library lab in Balubangjaya, Bogor, called Taman Baca Pustaka. PUSTAKA can serve the dual purpose of promoting literacy and increasing reading interest among the community while simultaneously expanding the dissemination of advanced, self-sufficient, and modern agricultural technology to the people of Bogor (Sembiring & Wijayanti, 2020).

This expansion has blurred the boundaries of functions and user coverage for special libraries. Socially inclusive libraries offer an opportunity for PUSTAKA to broaden its functions and services to a wider audience according to the information it manages, which is related to agriculture (Sembiring & Wijayanti, 2020). Here are various social inclusion activities conducted by PUSTAKA as a specialized library within the community:

Providing Community Skills Training

PUSTAKA's services go beyond offering digital information; they also provide socially inclusive services as a means of transforming the library. PUSTAKA in Bogor plays a significant role in enhancing the theoretical and practical knowledge of the community regarding agriculture. Previous research has shown that specialized libraries are transforming by expanding their service coverage and functions (Sembiring & Wijayanti, 2020).

In addition to being a center for knowledge with facilities, services, and various print and digital collections, PUSTAKA also acts as a cultural center and community activity hub (Sutarsyah, Rufaidah, & Suryantini, 2021). PUSTAKA's role in providing training and workshops in the Laboratory of Social Inclusion-Based PUSTAKA, Taman Baca PUSTAKA Darmaga,

encourages farmers and the community to apply agricultural science and technology. Hydroponic plant collections are educational tools to promote sustainable home gardening, especially for Women Farmers' Groups (KWT), enabling them to utilize their surroundings for sustainable food production.

Fig. 1. Training Activities on Hydroponic Plants for KWT

Source: pustaka.setjen.pertanian.go.id (PUSTAKA News, 2020c, 2020a)

Fig. 2. Vegetable Harvesting by KWT Group

The Laboratory of Social Inclusion-Based PUSTAKA, Taman Baca PUSTAKA Darmaga, has benefited the local community. This Laboratory become the activity center for the community, it provides a place for the community completed with library materials and other facilities to encourage them to develop community potential related to agriculture by some activities, such as trainings, workshops, reading, and other activities.

Fig. 3. The Launching of Laboratoty of PUSTAKA

Source: pustaka.setjen.pertanian.go.id (PUSTAKA News, 2020b)

The Locals views the laboratory as not just a place for reading books but also as a recreational center for urban agriculture due to its attractive and modern agricultural garden. Urban farming communities/Women Farmers' Groups use the Laboratory of PUSTAKA as a venue for community activities searching for literature to support their knowledge and understanding of farming (Lusiana et al., 2023). According to Lusiana et al. (2023), literacy programs at TBM can

help improve people's life skills by providing empowerment, training, and mentoring, which have a positive impact on individual abilities and skills.

In social inclusion activities, the Laboratory of Social Inclusion-Based PUSTAKA also serves as a central hub for the production and distribution of seeds to ensure the availability of plant supplies in each KWT member's home. This focus on urban farming aims to intensify the use of local resources for quality and diverse household food production, contributing to local food security (Junaidi, 2022). The agricultural literacy activities carried out by urban farming communities need to be replicated by the government to enhance the literacy and agricultural knowledge of the wider population.

Fig. 4. Training on Post-harvest for the Community by PUSTAKA

Source: pustaka.setjen.pertanian.go.id (PUSTAKA News, 2022)

This picture shows that PUSTAKA collaborated with private companies to hold technical guidance (bimtek) activity called "Training on Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for Postharvest Honey Potatoes". The utilization of the Laboratory of PUSTAKA, as mentioned by Suhendra (2022), serves as a maker space that contributes to entrepreneurship awareness, fosters a creative environment, and allows for the prototyping of innovative farming practices by KWT members. Makerspaces are understood as places providing various resources for patrons to develop creative ideas. Similarly, the Laboratory of PUSTAKA, as part of the Social Inclusion-Based Library program, offers a place for the community with library resources and other facilities to encourage the development of the community's agricultural potential.

As a Center for Agricultural Knowledge

PUSTAKA's role as a center for agricultural knowledge is evident, with a rich collection of agricultural resources dating back to 1842. The collection includes printed and electronic works, as well as various digital resources, both from Indonesia and abroad. PUSTAKA also subscribes to online journals to support its users (Sutarsyah, Syaikh, & Junaidi, 2021). PUSTAKA's digital collection is comprehensive and accessible online, thanks to the iTani portal, a repository of agricultural knowledge. PUSTAKA's vast collection of information, both in print and digital formats, also includes antiquarian books. Four distinct areas with unique functions complement PUSTAKA's offerings: (1) PUSTAKA Juanda 20, housing print and electronic collections, as well as antiquarian books; (2) the Digital Library of Agricultural Knowledge (P3D); (3) the Museum of Soil and Agriculture; and (4) Taman Baca Dramaga (Sutarsyah, Rufaidah, & Suryantini, 2021).

Fig. 5. Dissemination of Agricultural Information to the Public by PUSTAKA
Source: pustaka.setjen.pertanian.go.id (2023a)

Providing Information Technology-Based Library Services

Information technology and communication technologies can provide information over long distances. PUSTAKA utilizes this capability to expand its digital information services with virtual services. PUSTAKA launched the Virtual Literacy (VL) program in March 2020, focusing on agricultural literacy based on interactive communication to bring PUSTAKA's services to audiences in remote locations, tagged with the slogan "Library Comes to You" (Sutarsyah, Rufaidah, & Mulyandari, 2020). The Virtual Literacy program is expected to enable farmers to effectively use virtual information services, improving their understanding of agricultural practices and empowering them as entrepreneurs.

Fig. 6. Introduction to Organic Rice Cultivation through Virtual Literacy by PUSTAKA
Source: pustaka.setjen.pertanian.go.id (2023b)

The Virtual Reality program implemented by PUSTAKA is divided into four categories: (1) Virtual literacy for Ministry librarians; (2) Virtual literacy for researchers, extension workers, and policymakers in the Ministry of Agriculture; (3) Virtual literacy to support Strategic Development Command programs; and (4) Virtual literacy between Ministries and Agencies. Through virtual reality programs, farmers receive training in various aspects of agriculture and gain access to funding and guidance from planting to marketing, enabling them to achieve optimal profits.

Conclusion

In conclusion, PUSTAKA has extended its reach to communities with limited access to agricultural collections and information, contributing to the community by improving the skills of farmers related to crop pest management, from planting to post-harvest. The library has also become a maker space for entrepreneurship awareness and creativity, enhancing the potential of the community related to agriculture. PUSTAKA serves as a knowledge hub for agriculture, boasting a vast collection of agricultural resources. Furthermore, the library uses information technology to provide virtual services, expanding its reach and promoting agricultural literacy in remote areas. PUSTAKA's multifaceted approach to serving the community highlights its commitment to agricultural education and inclusive social services.

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YANTO A.

Кафедра бібліотекознавства та інформатики, Університет Паджаджаран (Бандунг, Індонезія), e-mail: andri.yanto@unpad.ac.id, ORCID 0000-0001-7041-0134

PRIJANA P.

Кафедра бібліотекознавства та інформатики, Університет Паджаджаран (Бандунг, Індонезія), e-mail: prijana@unpad.ac.id, ORCID 0000-0003-3290-0938

NURSARI T.

Лауреат премії LPDP (Бандунг, Індонезія), e-mail: tita19002@mail.unpad.ac.id, ORCID 0009-0001-5315-3460

Внесок спеціальних бібліотек у сприяння соціальній інтеграції в Індонезії

Мета. Більшість спеціальних бібліотек задовольняють інформаційні потреби свого робочого середовища, підтримуючи розвиток і вдосконалення обов'язків і функцій установи та її людських ресурсів. Проте кілька інновацій у сфері послуг було здійснено шляхом створення програм обслуговування для широкої громадськості, що базуються на соціальній інтеграції. Однією з них є Бібліотечний центр розповсюдження сільськогосподарських технологій (PUSTAKA) Міністерства сільського господарства Індонезії. Це дослідження має на меті надати огляд того, як спеціальна бібліотека PUSTAKA може бути залучена до створення інноваційних послуг для громадськості через програми соціальної інклюзії. **Методика.** Використано якісний метод бібліотечних досліджень з описовим підходом. **Результати.** Результати дослідження ілюструють, що PUSTAKA робить свій внесок у розвиток громади з обмеженими сільськогосподарськими колекціями та доступом до інформації. Бібліотека також стала мейкерським простором для підприємницької обізнаності та креативності, підвищуючи потенціал громади, пов'язаний із сільським господарством. PUSTAKA є центром знань з сільськогосподарської тематики, маючи у своєму розпорядженні величезні ресурси по сільському господарству. Крім того, бібліотека використовує інформаційні технології для надання віртуальних послуг, розширюючи охоплення та сприяючи підвищенню сільськогосподарської грамотності у віддалених районах. Багатогранний підхід PUSTAKA до служіння громаді підкреслює її відданість сільськогосподарській освіті та інклюзивним соціальним послугам. **Висновки.** Дослідження дійшло висновку, що PUSTAKA як спеціальна бібліотека впровадила соціальну інклюзію, зробивши свій внесок у розвиток сільськогосподарської освіти в регіоні.

Ключові слова: соціальна інтеграція; трансформація бібліотеки; спеціальна бібліотека; інформаційні послуги

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